
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF AGRICULTURAL SOLAR PANELS WITH REGARD TO EMISSION RADIATION THROUGH A TWO-AXIS CONTROL SYSTEM

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Abstract. Photovoltaic (PV) systems are rapidly developing around the world, but embedded (PV) devices are often installed as static planar systems with precise predetermined angles. This paper focuses on the development of a closed-loop solar tracking system (STS) to accurately measure the location of the Sun in real time, allowing the system to move solar panels. To ensure maximum solar radiation reaches the panel surface, a sensor-based mechanical controller adjusts the sunlight intensity on the surface, rotates the two-axis motor tracking system, and directs the photovoltaic panel toward the sun. The system, consisting of an electrical and mechanical system, was developed using the PVsyst 7.4-Trial platform and the Grid-Connected platform for real solar observer systems. Grid-Connected simulation results show that in orientation, the tracker stand structure for two 530W PV panels was securely attached to the base enough to withstand normal wind speeds. These systems provide 25% power generation efficiency during the summer season compared to a bi-axial PV system with real-time solar tracker installed on a static base.

Keywords: solar panel, radiation, Crystal (mono, poly, multi) Various silicon solar cell, biaxial controlled sensor system, electricity, efficiency.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11079819>

Introduction

Currently, there is a lot of talk about the prospect of renewable energy sources. For example, the amount of energy that radiation from the sun receives on the planet is on average 1.3-1.4 kW/m². When we do not take into account the amount of radiation that travels back into space from the atmosphere, there is an average of 1 kW/m² of energy on the surface of the Earth. This energy is 9,000 times more than the energy needs of the planet at the same time. For this reason, the newly added energy capacity is being implemented at the expense of renewable sources, not conventional energy[1].

There are several methods and ways to assess and increase the efficiency of solar panels, which include:

Depending on the type of solar elements, its efficiency is distinguished. Today, more than 90 percent of solar elements on the market are made on a Silicon basis. Depending on the type of Crystal (mono, Poly, multi), structure and other technical and technological solutions, silicon solar elements are distinguished and differ in efficiency. In the Uzbek market, solar panels with a polycrystalline silicon-based (16÷17)% efficiency are mainly sold. Some PERC (passivated emitter rear contact) and shj (silicon heterojunction solar cells) solar elements have higher efficiency than 22%. Unfortunately, it is difficult to distinguish the quality of the device at a glance due to the similarity of the appearance of the solar panels. Therefore, the consumer does not always buy a quality solar panel. It is almost impossible to assess the quality of the solar panel without checking it through special devices. Therefore, when installing solar panels, it is necessary to consult a specialist[4].

The efficiency of solar panels is also influenced by the climatic conditions of the location of the panels. The manufacturer tests the solar elements and panels in a special laboratory before launching them for sale. Indicators must meet the established standards of the characteristic of solar panels. The same indicators are written on the device passport. And we buy products based on this characteristic. The problem is that the values of the characteristic indicated in the passport

corresponding to the climatic conditions of the Mediterranean Sea are presented. That is, in order for the characteristic shown in the passport to be fully manifested in practice, winter should be mild ($10\div 16$) $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and summer dry and moderately warm ($22\div 30$) $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Air humidity should be $50\div 65\%$ in summer and $65\div 80\%$ in winter. Solar panels are tested in conditions close to this climate, the characteristic of which is written. To be even more precise, 1000 W / m^2 of radiation, with an air mass coefficient of 1.5 panels temperature of 25°C for the solar spectrum, the conditions are standard test conditions (STS) [3,4].

Control and monitoring systems should be established. With the help of control and monitor systems and programs at the station, the state of electricity on each panel is monitored and tracked. Through such systems, it is possible to verify that the panels work in the position where the efficiency and tips are given now[4].

It is also possible to increase the efficiency of solar panels by cleaning them from dust particles covered in the surface. Solar panels can be cleaned through several methods. The main ones of these methods are as follows. This includes self-cleaning and solar panel monitoring system, automatic cleaning of solar panels based on microcontroller, electrostatic dust removal, mechanical dust particle cleaning[2].

Since solar panels convert the radiation coming from the sun into electrical energy of the moment, solar radiation must be maximally steeped on the surface of the panel to obtain maximum energy. Light returned from the surface of the panels without absorption does not work in the energy generation. Therefore, when installing solar panels on the farm, it is necessary to rely on a professional project. After all, the project that corresponds to your neighbor may not correspond to your home. To do this, there must be conditions for the place where solar panels will be installed in your home to receive the energy coming from the sun during the day in a maximally upright position. An important role in this is played by the angle of installation of the panels, the configuration of the panels. In the location where the angle of installation of the panels is located, the location relative to the sun is taken into account. When performing these calculations, special devices and sputnik data are used, as well as the measurement is taken extremely accurately, the panels will approach the expected result to the maximum[3,4].

There are ways to improve the efficiency of solar panels even through sensory mechanical control systems of the PV system, which provide a steep descent of the surface relative to the solar radiation that is falling. To ensure maximum solar radiation to fall on the panel surface, the sensor-based mechanical controller adjusts the intensity of sunlight to the surface, the engine rotates the two-axis tracking system circuit, and focuses the PV system to the sun[4].

This article analyzes a sensor-based mechanically controlled system that provides maximum solar radiation to the surface of the PV system. The article describes the PV type lr5-72hbd-530m manufactured at LONGi Green Energy Technology Co Ltd of the Chinese state with a total capacity of $P_{um}=1060\text{w}$, and the technical characteristics of the panel are as follows. Rated working state power $P_{max}=530\text{w}$, voltage at P_{max} (V_{mp}) 41.35 V , P_{max} (I_{mp}) 12.82 A , open electronic voltage (V_{oc}) 49.20 V , short circuit current (I_{qt}) 13.71 a , power tolerance $0\sim 3\%$, V_{OC} and I_{qt} tolerances $\pm 3\%$, Maximum system voltage $\text{DC}1500\text{V}$ (IEC/UL), Operating Temperature $-40^{\circ}\text{C}\sim +85^{\circ}\text{C}$ it was analyzed that these solar device non-controllable and mechanically controlled systems of PV surface with respect to solar radiation[5].

Method 1

In Table 1, its data were obtained at an average value between 8:00 a.m. and 6:00 p.m. during the summer season from unguided solar devices with respect to the steep angle of incidence of sunlight installed at the Faculty of energy of the Institute of counter engineering and Economics in Qarshi. This table includes the outside air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), solar panel body temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), the amount of radiation that falls on the 1m^2 surface of the solar panel (W/m^2), the total (aperture)

surface of the solar panel (m²), the total solar radiation amount that falls on the panel surface (W), the electrical power produced (W), as well as the I.K lari are listed. Using data, time-dependence graphs of the total amount of solar radiation falling on the surface of the panel, and time-dependence graphs of the electrical power generated.

Parameters obtained from 8:00 to 18:00 in an uncontrollable PV system

Table 1.

No	Time (hours)	Outside air temperature $t_{i,h}$, °C	Solar panel body temperature $t_{p,kor}$, °C	Falling solar radiation q_p , W/m ²	Solar panel overview Surface F , m ²	Total solar radiation falling on the surface of the panel $Q_p = q_p \cdot F$, W	produced electric energy, N_{el} , W	F.I.K $\eta = N_{el}/Q_p$ %
1	8:00	26	38,73	352	4,84	1703,68	274	16,08
2	9:00	30	45,91	540	4,84	2613,6	512	19,59
3	10:00	33	48,01	740	4,84	3581,6	708	19,77
4	11:00	36	58,08	916	4,84	4433,44	726	16,38
5	12:00	37	60,72	1016	4,84	4917,44	684	13,91
6	13:00	39	63,45	1025	4,84	4961	762	15,36
7	14:00	39	62,18	950	4,84	4598	760	16,53
8	15:00	38	56,94	820	4,84	3968,8	724	18,24
9	16:00	38	50,83	630	4,84	3049,2	578	18,96
10	17:00	36	42,74	395	4,84	1911,8	346	18,1
11	18:00	35	34,95	144	4,84	696,96	148	21,24
<i>O'rt</i>		35,18	51,14	684,36		3312,3	565,63	17,64

Figure 1. Uncontrollable QEQ $Q_p=f(t)$ summer season characteristic[3]

Figure 2. Uncontrollable QEQ $N_{el}=f(t)$ summer season characteristic[4]

Assuming this graph, the average radiation that falls on the surface of the panel 1m² is $q_p=684.6 \text{ w/m}^2$, the average value of the total amount of solar radiation that falls on the Panel surface is $Q_p=q_p \cdot F=3312.3 \text{ w}$, as well as the average value of the electrical power produced is $N_{el}=565.63 \text{ W}$. When the surface of the solar panel is installed uncontrollably with respect to the steep angle of incidence of sunlight from 8:00 to 18:00 for the summer season in a day, an average of 11 hours a day produces $A_k=6.22 \text{ kW} \cdot \text{h}$ of electricity. The duration of the summer season is calculated from the beginning of April to the beginning of September, which is $N=183$ days, and for the summer season, $AUM=A_k \cdot n=6.22 \cdot 183=1138.26 \text{ kW} \cdot \text{h}$ produces electricity[5].

Figure 1. Front and rear view of the touch-controlled PV system with respect to the angle of incidence of two-axis sunlight[4].

This system was developed using the PVsyst 7.4-TRIAL datur and the true solar Observer systems Grid-Connected platform as I.

Method 2

Parameters obtained in the controlled PV system from 8:00 to 18:00

Table 2.

N_0	Time (hours)	Outside air temperature $t_{t,h}, ^\circ C$	Solar panel body temperature $t_{p,kor}, ^\circ C$	Falling solar radiation $q_p, \text{ W/m}^2$	Solar panel overview Surface $F, \text{ m}^2$	Total solar radiation falling on the surface of the panel $Q_p=q_p \cdot F, \text{ W}$	electric produced energy, $N_{el}, \text{ W}$	F.I.K $\eta=N_{el}/Q_p \%$
1	8:00	26	38,73	672	4,84	3253,6	523,27	16,08
2	9:00	30	45,91	739	4,84	3579	701,12	19,59
3	10:00	33	48,01	832	4,84	4028,4	796,32	19,77
4	11:00	36	58,08	936	4,84	4531,4	742,04	16,38
5	12:00	37	60,72	1016	4,84	4917,4	683,99	13,91
6	13:00	39	63,45	1025	4,84	4961	762	15,36
7	14:00	39	62,18	977	4,84	4729,6	781,75	16,53
8	15:00	38	56,94	955	4,84	4625	843,71	18,24
9	16:00	38	50,83	950	4,84	4602,8	872,5	18,96
10	17:00	36	42,74	832	4,84	4028,4	729,06	18,1
11	18:00	35	34,95	671	4,84	3250,8	690,31	21,24
<i>O'rt</i>		35,18	51,14	873,18		4227,94	738,73	194,1

In Table 2, the data of the solar panel installed at the Faculty of energy of the Institute of counter-engineering and Economics in Qarshi city was obtained at an average value in the summer season from 8:00 a.m. to 18:00 p.m. from the solar devices I propose, controlled with respect to the steep angle of incidence of sunlight. This table includes the outside air temperature (C°), solar panel body temperature (C°), the amount of radiation that falls on the 1m² surface of the solar panel (W/m²), the total (aperture) surface of the solar panel (m²), the total solar radiation amount

that falls on the Panel surface (W), the electrical power produced (W), as well as the I.K lari are listed. Using data, time-dependence graphs of the total amount of solar radiation falling on the surface of the panel, and time-dependence graphs of the electrical power generated.

Figure 3. Controlled QEQ $Q_p=f(t)$ summer season characteristic[3]

Figure 4. Managed QEQ $N_{el}=f(t)$ summer season characteristic[4]

This graph can be seen to be slightly aligned with the graph of the solar radiation relatively uncontrollable PV system, i.e. with respect to the falling solar radiation, the average radiation of the PV system panel falling on the $1m^2$ surface is $q_p=873,18 W/m^2$, the average value of the total solar radiation power falling on the Panel surface is $Q_p=q_p \cdot f=4227,94 W$, Taking it as an average 11-hour solar day in the summer season from 8:00 to 18:00, in one day $A_k=8,12 kW \cdot h$ produces electricity[4].

With respect to two-axis falling solar radiation, the PV system is installed with sensory mechanical control in one day during an average 11-hour day from 8:00 to 18:00 a.m. for the summer season, the $A_k=8,12 kW \cdot h$ produces electricity-the duration of the summer season is calculated from April to September OHI, it is $N=183$ days, and for the summer season $A_{um}=A_k \cdot N=8,12 \cdot 183=1485,96 kW \cdot h$

The parameters of the solar panel with installed maximum power $P_{max}=1060W$ were analyzed according to two options.

Under Option 1, a solar panel mounted on an uncontrollable static base relative to the steep angle of incidence of sunlight produces $A_{um1}=A_k \cdot N=6,22 \cdot 183=1138,26 kW \cdot h$ of electrical energy during the summer season.

Under Option 2, while the PV system is controlled by a sensory mechanical with respect to the steep angle of incidence of two-axis sunlight, $A_{um2}=A_k \cdot N=8,12 \cdot 183=1485,96 kW \cdot h$ produces electrical energy[3.5].

Results

The electric energy difference between a controlled and an unguided solar panel device is $\Delta A_{um}=A_{um2}-A_{um1}=347,7 kW \cdot h$. In this case, the solar panel operates at a nominal voltage of the sensor mechanically controlled device mechanism $U_{nom}=220 V$ with respect to the steep angle of incidence of sunlight, the total power of the two-axis mechanism engine is $P_m=90 W$, operating in

a repeated short-term mode of operation, and its connecting duration is $UD=15\%$. Its one-day consumption is $P_{mk} = P_m \sqrt{UD} = 0,09 \sqrt{0,15} = 0,034 kW$ daily electricity consumption $A_{mk} = P_{mk} \cdot t = 0,034 \cdot 11 = 0,38 kW$ if we calculate per season $A_{mum} = A_{mk} \cdot N = 0,38 \cdot 183 = 70,16 kW \cdot h$ subtracting the electrical energy that the mechanism desires from the two options electrical energy difference $\Delta A_f = \Delta A_{um} - A_{mum} = 347,7 - 70,16 = 277,53 kW \cdot h$ can make a profit. These calculations were calculated for a panel with installed capacity $P_n = 1060w$, found according to the ratio coefficient for a solar device with a larger capacity[6].

Conclusion

In conclusion, scientists are currently doing a lot of research to improve the efficiency of solar panels. In turn, a sensor-based PV system that provides a steep descent of the PV system relative to the sunlight falling on the surface can be increased to 25% of the electricity generated on the panel by a touch-controlled system relative to the radiation of the falling sun.

The result of the studies shows that one of the most effective methods of a sensory mechanically controlled system that provides a steep descent of solar panels relative to the sun's light falling on the surface is the control of solar panels using an electrical circuit operating at a source of $U_{nom} = 220v$ alternating current operating in the repeated short term. Because the effect of this method is much lower energy consumption compared to other methods has been observed by studies.

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